

Numerical study of electroporation of cells by helium atmospheric pressure plasma jet

C. Anastassiou¹, N. Charalambous², C. Lazarou^{1,3}, and G. E. Georghiou^{1,3}

¹ENAL Electromagnetics and Novel Applications Lab, Department of Electrical and Computer Engineering, University of Cyprus, Cyprus

²Department of Physics, University of Cyprus, Nicosia, 1678, Cyprus

³Faculty FOSS Research Centre for Sustainable Energy, Department of Electrical and Computer Engineering, University of Cyprus, Nicosia, Cyprus

LONG TERM GOAL: CANCER TREATMENT

When considering surgical treatment of cancer it would be ideal to have a way to **selectively** destroy cancerous cells while leaving healthy cells intact. Atmospheric pressure plasma jet (APPJ) has shown this selectivity.[1,2].

MOTIVATION: PLASMA ELECTROPORATION

Test the hypothesis that induced selective apoptosis is caused by the built up of electric fields across the cell membrane that cause reversible electroporation for the cancerous but not the healthy cells. This means that the cancerous cell membrane opens up during the presence of the electric field and allows for the penetration of the plasma generated RNOS such as $\bullet\text{NO}$, $\bullet\text{OH}$, O , H_2O_2 causing apoptosis while leaving the healthy tissue intact. [3]. In this work Plasma is studied only for its ability to induce electroporation

PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

- MODEL DEVELOPMENT:** A two dimensional axii-symmetric model that considers a gas dynamic model (GDM) and a plasma fluid model (PFM) was developed [3]
- VOLTAGE ACROSS DIELECTRIC:** Plasma interacts with a dielectric surface that represents the average electrical properties of the tissue to obtain overall voltage
- TMV:** The calculated voltage across the dielectric is used in a new model that considers the analytical geometry of normal and cancerous cells in order to investigate its effect on the TMV

4. CELL MODEL

Applied voltage (from Plasma fluid model)

	Permittivity	Conductivity (S/m)
Membrane	5	$3 \cdot 10^{-7}$
Cytoplasm	72.5	0.3
Nucleus	42	1.03
Extra cellular fluid	72.5	1.2

SIGNIFICANCE

Larger cells (such as cancerous cells) tend to have higher TMV and which could lead to electroporation and therefore treatment of cancerous cells while the normal cells remain unaffected

RESULTS

Normal Cell (NC)

Cancer Cell (CC1)

TRANSMEMBRANE VOLTAGE

REFERENCES

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